

"Some useful ways to learn English"

Anvarjonova Umida Salimovna

Student of the Termez state Pedagogical institute (foreign language and literature)

Abstract:in this article discusses about the useful ways of learning English and gives useful information about this.

Key words: some types of learning English, language learning strategy, Methods , discussion , communicating in this language , technology.

Nowadays English is not an ordinary language , it is more than language. English language is an international language . Many people use English language to communicate with people in different countries. It can easily link you to people around the world. Furthermore, learning English can help you to reach the goals. It gives us more opportunity to get well paid job. In addition to that, learning English also can improve students' life skills. It has been found that students can develop better vocabularies and an improved level of literacy all through a studying a foreign language .

In these days students can have different problems and difficulties in learning English.

Language Learning Strategy (LLS) is really important and plays big role in a learning process. Therefore , it is interesting to know what strategies that successful and unsuccessful learners use in learning English so that it gives some information to the teacher , especially to help students to learn Learning Strategies that are less fun or arguably boring will not improve students' English skills to be better, instead make students feel bored and lazy to learn . Teachers should change the learning activity into the fun. However , the most important thing is that students enjoy every learning process as something enjoyable. It may help students feel comfortable during the learning . Fun learning activities will have an impact on improving students' English abilities naturally. Students tend to like fun learning. They may begin with learning from something interesting. Having fun while learning can build students' interest in learning English. Here are some important ways to learn English language. Mingling with foreigners is a good way to improve students' speaking activity. For example students can go to tourist resort and get a job to improve their speaking skills and communicate with them rare.

The next way of learning English is listening to slow songs . Listening slow songs is the easiest way to improve their listening skills. Students can learn a lot by listening to slow songs , especially about grammar, new vocabulary and pronunciation aspects from songs. The students will not be bored to learn English language by listening slow songs every day. On the other hand , listening to slow song can be the best way to calm the minds of students.

Another way of learning English language is from technology. Technology plays a huge impact on teaching and learning process. Technology can be a media for teacher to teach various types of subjects, and one of them is English. Watching their favourite film or show in English language may be the ways

for students to learn English in a good and interesting way. The students should spend 5 hours per days to watch English show to improve their listening and vocabulary skills. Furthermore students may easily learn English by using the net. For instance they can be in touch with foreigners in their website such as telegram, what's up, Instagram , Twitter, Facebook and YouTube. Nowadays, YouTube has been a daily expenditure for people around the globe, especially for teenagers. There are many educational videos that can be watched by the students to help them learn English easily. By watching videos , students get a new knowledge and improve listening ability. Watching videos on YouTube gives to students the chance to memorize their favourite video material easily. Another way to improve English is listening to radio . Radio encourages the students imagination through words and sounds. The most important way to improve their speaking and writing aspects is chatting or emailing in English language. It can be the way to improve students' vocabulary and confidence also. Those ways are not only improve students' interest in learning English but also helping to student to learn English naturally.

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